

NNLM Reading Club Toolkit

September 2022

Preface

This [NNLM Reading Club](#) Toolkit addresses two calls for action. The first is from NNLM Coordinators, who sought to understand the purpose of the NNLM Reading Club, how they might use it, and how to promote it through outreach. The second is from public librarians, who asked how to host health book club discussions and apply the NNLM Reading Club resources to their other work. This toolkit meets both needs.

The toolkit is divided into different sections:

- The history and evolution of the NNLM Reading Club, which describes why it came about and how it is produced today. You'll also find our selection criteria in this section.
- Community outreach, which explains NNLM Reading Club goals and how the Reading Club supports key NNLM initiatives.
- Health Book Club Tips, which shares ideas for facilitating health book club discussions in different types of library and organizational settings; explains resources on the NNLM Reading Club website; and offers guidelines for creating a safe space for health book club discussions and for responding to health information questions. Lastly, it suggests how to respond to someone whose previous trauma experience may be triggered in a health book club discussion.

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Section 1: History and Evolution of the NNLM Reading Club

Agency Support

The Network of the National Library of Medicine (NNLM) is the external engagement and training arm of the National Library of Medicine (NLM), one of the twenty-seven National Institutes of Health (NIH). NNLM comprises seven academic health science libraries across the United States and more than 10,000 member organizations. The Network supports the National Library of Medicine's mission to provide researchers, health professionals, public health workers, educators and the public with equal access to biomedical and health information resources and data.

Figure 1 Organization of the Network of the National Library of Medicine

In 2017, the National Library of Medicine received a supplementary award from NIH *All of Us*, an historic effort to collect and study data from one million or more diverse people living in the United States with the goal of advancing precision medicine.ⁱ With this funding, NNLM hired community engagement librarians to help raise awareness of precision medicine and medical research while building health information capacity with libraries to address the priority health concerns of persons Underrepresented in Biomedical Research (UBR).ⁱⁱ

Program Development

For public libraries, book discussions are a familiar and popular program. As an enjoyable group activity, they offer intrinsic value such as improved vocabulary, comprehension, and conversation skills. Since book discussion groups, in general, are entertaining and beneficial, it makes sense that a health-themed reading group would have similar advantages. Because health issues may be difficult to understand or have an attached stigma, people who voluntarily gather to read an agreed-upon book ought to feel safe discussing and asking questions in a relaxed, trustworthy space. The social connections and exchange of information will improve awareness and increase empathy in support of health literacy.

Considering the expertise and effort required to identify compelling books on health and medical topics, as well as packaging ready-to-use *free* book discussion guides,

customizable promotional materials, and NIH and NLM information resources, organizers believed library staff would trust the expertise of the NNLM and find it easy to implement a health-themed book club discussion if NNLM performed the “heavy lifting.” This proved to be the case.

Through the enjoyment and intimacy of a book club, readers can discuss health and wellness topics important to them and their loved ones.

In the summer of 2018, after writing, submitting, and receiving program approval, a cross-regional collaboration launched national outreach of the NNLM Reading Club. Darlene Kaskie of the University of Iowa, Michele Spatz of the University of Washington, and George Strawley of the University of Utah worked as an ad-hoc team, meeting weekly via Zoom to select books that aligned with the priority health topics of NNLM and monthly National Health Observances.ⁱⁱⁱ

From November 2018 through March 2020, with significant contributions from NNLM office staff, the Regional Medical Libraries purchased and shipped books to requesting libraries that met the UBR criteria. During this period, it is estimated that the NNLM Reading Club distributed 788 kits reaching over 6,300 readers nationwide who discussed health and wellness representing 21 health topics and 79 book titles.

First books selected for the NNLM Reading Club featured Family Health History, a National Health Observance recognized on Thanksgiving Day, November 2018

A standard NNLM Reading Club Book Kit included 8 regular print books and, if available, alternative formats such as large print or audio might be substituted upon request; 1 library book bag; 8 book totes; 8 discussion guides; and relevant collateral health information.

Evaluation

In addition to the number of book kits requested, the NNLM Reading Club proved successful as evidenced by survey results, appreciative notes and photos.

Figure 2 Underrepresented in Biomedical Research Populations: The Number of Libraries that Targeted the Population and the Number that Reported they Reached the Population

Figure 3 NNLM Reading Club Ratings 1=Strongly Agree; 2=Strongly Disagree; N=94

Evolution

By March 2020, with the threat of the ongoing spread of COVID-19 in the United States, in-person activities everywhere, including libraries, halted. NNLM Reading Club discontinued book kit shipments as a public safety precaution but continued its monthly online program, and developed a virtual author talk online series through April 2021.

NNLM Reading Club Presents...
an afternoon with
Alfredo Quinones-Hinojosa, M.D.

He'll join our host, Edgar Gil Rico, NAHH, to discuss his book, *Becoming Dr. Q: My Journey from Migrant Farm Worker to Brain Surgeon*. Dr. Q as he is known, shares his journey from a child in a Mexican village to migrant farmworker in California to world-renown brain surgeon and researcher. Dr. Q will also answer audience questions.

Jan. 14, 2021 - 3-4 pm ET 2-3 pm CT 1-2 pm MTN 12-1 PT
Join us at: https://youtu.be/6X0-TS_rvKQ

Logos for NIH, All of Us, Gundersen, Marshfield Clinic Health Systems, NHCQA, National Alliance on Hispanic Health, NAHH, and Wisconsin are visible at the bottom of the poster.

NNLM Reading Club Presents...
From July 2020 through April 2021, the *NNLM Reading Club Presents...* featured five authors who discussed their books and addressed relevant health topics. Organizations, such as the National Association of Hispanic Health who also were funded by *All of Us*, partnered with the NNLM Reading Club. Their participation introduced NNLM and health information to an even widening number of UBR population groups such as African American and Hispanic/Latino/a people. Additionally, the University of Washington Regional Medical Library contracted with a Seattle-based video production team. Their services improved the visual quality of the program and expanded media coverage, which also increased viewership.

After a brief hiatus as the NNLM restructured the Network, founding partners Darlene Kaskie, University of Iowa, Region 6; and Michele Spatz, University of Washington, Region 5, resumed NNLM Reading Club in January 2022. They developed a governing charter, and invited all interested members from the NNLM regions, offices, and centers. Representation now included Shannon Jones and Lorin Jackson from the Medical University of South Carolina, Region 2, as well as Tess Wilson and Stefania Acosta Ramirez from the National *All of Us* Program Center. The new alliance reinvigorated the program, focusing on emerging NNLM priorities such as health misinformation and racial disparities.

Section 2: Community Outreach: Book Clubs and Libraries

Why Host a Book Club?

“Reading has been proven to decrease blood pressure, lower heart rate, and reduce feelings of psychological distress. Beyond that, reading may even help you live longer. According to a 12-year study published in *Innovation in Aging*, participants who read books (opposed to other forms of media) lived approximately two years longer than those who didn’t read at all.”^{iv}

“Book clubs provide a wonderful forum for readers to talk about books and the reading experience and libraries contain many helpful resources for book groups.”^v

Why Host a Health-focused Book Club?

A health-focused book club allows libraries to better meet the information needs of their communities. If a library patron does not know where to search for health information or is unfamiliar with resources available through the library, a book club can connect to resources, as well as to build relationships throughout the community. A book club also addresses the issue of patron anxiety about information. We know there is an abundance of material at the library; sifting through can be stressful and overwhelming for the unaided patron.

By connecting with fellow community members who are also learning in a book club, as well as with library workers, patrons feel empowered to continue to develop their digital, health, and information literacy skills.

Why Host an NNLM Reading Club Book?

The Network of the National Library of Medicine (NNLM) has three primary initiatives for 2021-2026. These include:

- Bridging the Digital Divide
- Environmental Determinants of Health
- Confronting Health Misinformation

Hosting a health-focused book club directly addresses each of these larger NNLM initiatives with the community members who use library services.

Bridging the Digital Divide

A health-focused book club provides an opportunity to develop digital literacy skills. This is particularly relevant if the book club contains materials accessible online or if the book club is held in a digital format. Community members will then develop digital literacy skills while participating in the book club.

According to the Pew Research Center, “American’s digital literacy is lacking, with 40 percent of adults answering questions [pertaining to digital literacy] correctly on average”^{vi}

Librarians of various backgrounds and subject areas have a vested interest in addressing the lack of digital literacy skills in adults so patrons may successfully access more library materials. Fostering digital literacy in adults helps patrons achieve their information needs - not just health information, but all information.

Environmental Determinants of Health

The [Healthy People 2030 Initiative](#) defines social determinants of health as “the conditions in the environments where people are born, live, learn, work, play, worship, and age that affect a wide range of health, functioning, and quality-of-life outcomes and risks”^{vii}

HP2030 defines the five social determinants as:

- Economic Stability
- Education Access & Quality
- Health Care Access & Quality
- Neighborhood & Built Environment
- Social & Community Context

Reading clubs about health topics enable patrons and information professionals to discuss how social factors influence their health access. Reading clubs encourage community members to be better informed about health care decisions.

Confronting Health Misinformation

Along with bridging the digital divide and unpacking environmental determinants of health, confronting health misinformation is part of the reading club mission. People frequent public libraries for all kinds of information. Especially with the COVID-19 pandemic, public libraries must be better equipped with current, trusted health information. Reading clubs provide a way for library workers to share updated, trustworthy health information. Library workers can also connect patrons with resources such as MedlinePlus and PubMed or local health organizations through reading club participation.

Using the NNLM Reading Club Materials

The NNLM Reading Club Interest Group, the group responsible for creating the monthly NNLM Reading Club materials, consists of health sciences and medical librarians with subject matter expertise who curate and provide resources for reading clubs. Their primary objectives are to support and respect library staff time and develop health literacy with the library community.

Saves Time for Library Staff

The NNLM Reading Club directly supports library staff's limited planning time and capacity to host a book club focused on a health theme.

By not only curating the inclusion of books related to national health themes and months, but also providing background information about each book along with supplementary materials, the NNLM Reading Club saves library staff time. The NNLM Reading Club provides:

- Monthly health topics with carefully selected featured books from across different genres
- Free, downloadable promotional materials
- Free, downloadable discussion guides
- Additional resources, such as author information and interviews

“ Why use the NNLM Reading Club?
Reading is healthy! Different studies report that reading improves memory, enhances empathy, and reduces stress. Reading also is a fundamental way to acquire knowledge, so it stands to reason that reading different health topics can help people make informed decisions about their own health and the health of their loved ones while reducing the stigma surrounding some diseases and health conditions.”

Darlene Kaskie, NNLM *All of Us* Community Engagement Coordinator

The NNLM Reading Club website includes free discussion guides to accompany each book along with deeper dive materials if book club participants would like to learn more. The Reading Club always includes additional resources to encourage and inspire more research by participants, thus developing their skills and addressing NNLM initiatives.

Therefore, a library worker with little health information experience can still conduct a reading group using the pre-packaged materials. This browsable, grab-'n-go online approach benefits library staff who wish to further health literacy efforts within the library and out into the greater community.

Develops Health Literacy

Another objective of the Reading Club is to connect the public with free NNLM resources, such as [MedlinePlus](#) and [PubMed](#). These and other health websites may feel intimidating, perhaps even to librarians, but by diving in and learning how to use these tools, we can better improve health literacy and information access for all.

With Patrons

Developing public health literacy requires a multi-pronged, multidirectional approach. One of the ways patrons can better understand trusted health information is through participation or facilitation of book club groups.

Libraries can support this effort by providing resources for different health-themed books. The intention is to encourage patrons to learn new information, as well as connect with their community through discussions about a book's health topic. Providing opportunities for patrons to share individual experiences with different health topics also encourages diverse perspectives. This aligns with the library's inclusive programming.

With Staff

The library staff's health literacy skills can also develop through health book club discussions. To become well-informed health information professionals, library staff need to be comfortable with an array of health topics. Improving library staff's knowledge of health topics allows them to guide patrons toward library resources. Ultimately, library staff are empowered to support patrons' health literacy, thus fostering individual and family health.

[Navigating the NNLM Reading Club Website](#)

The NNLM Reading Club website is a content-rich website. It identifies books that focus on specific health topics in an interesting and engaging way. Also, each featured book meets the Reading Club's selection criteria, which are:

- Author or book is award-winning or a national bestseller
- Consistent, positive book reviews or reader ratings
- Published within the past five years unless the title is considered a classic work
- Diverse author voices are represented
- All genres are considered: fiction, non-fiction, graphic medicine, Young Adult etc.
- Available in another format such as an audio, e-book, or large print
- Reading guide or book discussion guide available or NNLM Reading Club team member agrees to create one

Everything needed to host a book club discussion is found within the NNLM Reading Club pages – compelling health issues, featured books, interesting author information, print and social media promotional materials, customizable and downloadable discussion guides. Health science librarians share trusted information for book club participants who want to learn more.

The Reading Club's "Home Page" briefly describes the current month's selected topic and showcases the three featured books. A link from the home page takes users to the

current topic's main page, which has all the information to host a book club on any of the featured titles.

Other information located on the Home Page includes:

- **About the NNLM Reading Club** - Explains how the Reading Club began; how the Reading Club supports the work of library staff; and the Reading Club's selection criteria
- **Health Topics and Featured Books** – Comprehensive menu of health topics and book titles
- ***NNLM Reading Club Collection 2018 – 2021*** - Downloadable guide to all the topics covered, books featured, discussion guides, recommended health resources for the health topics addressed and links to book club discussion promotional materials for each of the featured books from 2018 – 2021.
- **And the Rest of the Story** – Archived and other materials including author talks and this Toolkit!

Section 3: Health Book Club Tips

Frequency of Offering a Health Book Club

So, how often should you offer health book club discussions? The answer depends on your book club participants! To be successful, build your meetings around your participants' schedules and preferences.

The NNLM Reading Club lends itself well to public library adult book groups. We suggest facilitating a health book discussion 1- 4 times per year to foster knowledge, explore important health issues and support health literacy.

With the inclusion of Young Adult (YA) book titles as well as Graphic Medicine titles for some health topics, Reading Club resources facilitate Youth Book Club discussions by public library or school library staff. Like the adult book group, we recommend facilitating a health book club discussion 1- 4 times per year for the same reasons noted above: to foster knowledge, explore important health issues and support health literacy.

Academic Health Sciences Librarians may use Reading Club materials in a couple of different ways. First, to facilitate a health book club hosted by health sciences library staff for students, faculty and staff. Secondly, the Reading Club website and resources can promote faculty-led book discussion groups. Faculty may host book club discussions for their department faculty or with their students. An interesting application is to offer the Reading Club as an interprofessional education activity, drawing health sciences students from different disciplines to share their diverse perspectives and approaches to the health issue being discussed.

Assisted Living facilities' residents or residents of senior care homes may appreciate having health topics addressed in their book club discussion groups from time to time.

And depending upon the community, a public library may want to promote one of the NNLM Reading Club selections as a community-wide, "Everybody Reads" event. This would make a wonderful tie-in during October's Health Literacy Month. ^{viii}

Creating a Safe Space for Health Book Club Discussions

Library staff have expressed concern about facilitating a book club discussion focused on a health topic. This is understandable given the personal nature of individuals' health experiences. There are some things you can do to promote an interesting discussion and yet protect privacy. The most crucial step is to establish behavioral agreements at the onset of the meeting. The goal is to create a safe space. These are two common ways to establish book club behavioral agreements:

First, asking participants to define what they need for safe engagement. As the book club facilitator, you may contribute important agreements to the list if no one else shares them. Here is a list of potential agreements to consider:

- No one is required to share any personal or privileged information;
- We will respect the privacy and confidentiality of what is shared;
- We will listen with empathy;
- We listen as much as we talk;
- We will not interrupt;
- We will honor emotions shared;
- We will treat each other with kindness and respect

Secondly, agreements may be defined by the facilitator who creates them based upon previous experience or by referencing behavioral code of conduct agreements from other professional organizations. Before the book club discussion begins, the group agreements will be shared and participants will be asked for verbal consent. Here are some behavioral agreements designed to foster safe spaces for sharing discussions:

- [GLSEN's Guidelines for Respectful GSA Spaces](#)
- [Ground Rules for Respectful Discussion](#) (Princeton University)
- [Conference on Inclusion & Diversity in Library and Information Science Guidelines for Engaging in Respectful & Productive Dialogue](#) (University of Maryland)
- [Can We Talk? Tips For Respectful Conversations in Schools, Workplaces And Communities](#) (ADL – Anti-Defamation League)

Being Trauma-Informed

Despite our best efforts, we can unintentionally trigger someone as a facilitator or as a member of a reading group. In fact, generally some health topics can be triggering and difficult to engage with others.

A Librarian's Story

"I was talking to one of our participants this morning who was very quiet during our discussion last night. She said she wanted to participate more but every time she started to talk, she started tearing up.

She has a brother who her parents adopted at 10 months old, who had been in four foster homes already by that time, and who currently has problems with addiction.

His birth family struggled with addiction as well. She is sending the book with highlighted passages to her parents. She said it changed the way she thinks about him and provided her some relief, and she has hopes it will relieve some of the guilt her parents feel as well because they are amazing and kind of course, and blame themselves more than they should.

Thank you again for partnering with us on what was an impactful book for our participants."

We do want to note that challenging discussions can eventually lead your group to positive outcomes. Ideally, you are working together to process or unpack past experiences to move forward better informed and better prepared to discuss these health topics.

We have some strategies for how to navigate challenges that could arise around trauma in your reading groups:

- Focus on not re-creating harm and instead on healing or reconciliation
- Restate your intentions and values as a reading group, especially if harm has been caused
- Engage in inquisitive conversation if someone has been triggered, harmed, or offended
 - Ask what they need to feel welcomed, safe, and included again
 - Do they want to address this in the group or individually with the facilitator(s)?
- Ask questions respectfully to help the individual clarify how the harm was caused
 - Was it the topic itself or something else?
 - Was it a previous experience that prompted their reaction?
- Provide an opening disclaimer statement to your group, when possible, about the topic

- Anticipate what could be challenging for the participants and attempt to outline those issues in advance or reach out for support from colleagues
 - Especially reach out to subject experts, therapists, social workers, or medical care professionals for support with specific topics

Responding to Health Questions Raised Before, During or After a Health Book Club Meeting

Another concern shared by library staff is how to respond to participants' requests for additional health information related to the book's topic or for other personal health information. Similar to other reference requests, library staff should be aware of key health resources, either online or in the collection. [Medlineplus.gov](https://medlineplus.gov) is an excellent resource – offering a wealth of health information on hundreds of health conditions including prescription and over-the-counter drugs, medical tests and procedures. The site is bilingual – English and Spanish – with limited information in other languages. Produced by the National Library of Medicine, the website is accessible for free, provides evidence-based health information and is ad-free.

We recommend noting to book club participants that Library staff are not doctors and will not offer medical advice. The topical health information handouts provided by the NNLM Reading Club for each book are designed to be shared with book club members and are freely downloadable. Facilitators may simply share the topical website URLs.

To build confidence and skills in providing consumer health information, the NNLM offers free consumer health information classes in a variety of ways: on-demand, through structured online classes and topical webinars. Visit the [NNLM Training](#) page to browse available classes.

NNLM also supports the Medical Library Association's [Consumer Health Information Specialization \(CHIS\)](#) by offering training required to apply for the specialization and also by supporting the application fee to receive the specialization certificate.

Appendix A: Selected Trauma-Informed Resources

Author: Lorin Jackson

Books

Van der Kolk, Bessel A. 2015. *The Body Keeps the Score: Brain, Mind and Body in the Healing of Trauma*. New York, NY: Penguin Books.

Winfrey, Oprah and Bruce D. Perry. 2021. *What Happened to You?: Conversations on Trauma, Resilience, and Healing*. New York, NY: Flatiron Books.

Articles

[Access Intimacy \(2011/2017\) – M. Mingus](#)

Martin, E. R. (2019). Social justice and the medical librarian. *Journal of the Medical Library Association*, 107(3): 291-303. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC6579597>

Ostermeier, K., Medina-Craven, M. N., Camp, K. M., & Davis, S. E. (2022). Can I Be Me With You at Work? Examining Relational Authenticity and Discretionary Behaviors in the Workplace. *The Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 58(2), 316–345.

[Building Consentful Tech](#)

Websites

[GLSEN Guidelines for Discussion](#)

[Trauma Informed Oregon](#)

[Buffalo Center for Social Research](#)

[White Supremacy Culture](#)

Appendix B: Glossary

Consumer Health = Consumer health information is intended for potential or current users of medical services (all of us!). It is designed to be educational, and can help individuals make decisions about health-related behavior and medical treatments. It differs from clinical information—that is, information written by and for medical professionals—in that it is developed with the layperson in mind, involving less technical language and more user-friendly formats. Consumer health information may include resources about prevention, self-care and wellness, diseases and conditions, treatment, health care options, and more.

Digital Divide = The digital divide is a term that refers to the gap between demographics and regions that have access to modern information and communications technology (ICT), and those that don't or have restricted access. This technology can include the telephone, television, personal computers and internet connectivity.

Environmental Determinants of Health = The range of personal, social, economic, and environmental factors that influence health status are known as determinants of health.

Determinants of health fall under several broad categories:

- Policymaking
- Social factors
- Health services
- Individual behavior
- Biology and genetics

Health Literacy = Health literacy is the degree to which individuals have the capacity to obtain, process, and understand basic health information needed to make appropriate health decisions.

- Low health literacy is more prevalent among:
 - Older adults
 - Minority populations
 - Those who have low socioeconomic status
 - Medically underserved people

Health Misinformation = Information that is false, inaccurate, or misleading according to the best available evidence at the time.

Medically Underserved Areas/Populations = Medically Underserved Areas/Populations (MUA/P) are areas or populations designated by Health Resources &

Service Administration (HRSA) as having too few primary care providers, high infant mortality, high poverty or a high elderly population.

NIH = National Institutes of Health

NLM = National Library of Medicine, one of the National Institutes of Health

NNLM = Network of the National Library of Medicine, the “outreach arm” of the National Library of Medicine

Privileged Communication = Privileged communication in healthcare refers to communications that include private patient information that is protected by federal, state, and local laws in the U.S. and in other countries. [From [Interpreting Privileged Communication in Healthcare](#) by Kent Yunk. March 18, 2019.]

Public Health = Public health is the science of protecting and improving the health of people and their communities. This work is achieved by promoting healthy lifestyles, researching disease and injury prevention, and detecting, preventing and responding to infectious diseases. Overall, public health is concerned with protecting the health of entire populations. These populations can be as small as a local neighborhood, or as big as an entire country or region of the world.

RML = Regional Medical Library, one of 7 regional libraries across the United States that serve as home to an office of the Network of the National Library of Medicine. These Regional Medical Libraries are typically part of an academic health sciences library.

ROCs = Regions, Offices and Centers, the different parts of the Network of the National Library of Medicine.

Trauma = A deeply distressing or disturbing experience. Types of traumatic experiences include physical injury, mental injury, subjective experiences, and observed experiences.

Trauma-Informed Care (TIC) = Trauma-Informed Care understands and considers the pervasive nature of trauma and promotes environments of healing and recovery rather than practices and services that may inadvertently re-traumatize.

UBR = Underrepresented in Biomedical Research; a term used in the NIH's *All of Us* research program, which it defines as being comprised of:

- Women
- Racial and ethnic groups
- Sexual and gender minorities
- Disadvantaged backgrounds
- Low Socioeconomic Status (SES) (Income, Education, and Occupation)
- Physical or mental disabilities
- Geographically or culturally isolated environment
- Rural

Endnotes

ⁱ [All of Us Research Program Overview](#). National Institutes of Health *All of Us* Research Program. Retrieved 15 August 2022.

ⁱⁱ [All of Us Research Program National Advisory Child Health and Human Development Council: slide no. 10](#). Stephanie Devaney, Ph.D. January 31, 2017.

ⁱⁱⁱ [“National Health Observances.” U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Office of Disease Prevention and Health Promotion](#). Retrieved 15 August 2022.

^{iv} [Lifelong benefits of starting a book club and tips for starting your own](#). By Koelsch Communities. *The Seattle Times*. October 25, 2021.

^v [For Book Lovers: Book Clubs](#). ilovelibraries: An initiative of the American Library Association. Retrieved 15 August 2022.

^{vi} [A Visual Representation of America’s Digital Literacy](#). World Economic Forum. October 30, 2019.

^{vii} [Social Determinants of Health. Healthy People 2030](#). Office Disease Prevention and Health Promotion. Retrieved 15 August 2022.

^{viii} [Health Literacy Month](#). Institute for Healthcare Advancement (IHA). Retrieved 15 August 2022.